

Contemporary Education Policy Analysis for Sustainable Development

Deepak Sharma, SCRIET, C.C.S University, Meerut -250004, India

Abstract

A case study of education policy analysis in the university system is reported and critically examined in this paper. The government's recent adoption of a new education strategy in universities and implementation of the old one has caused a paradigm change in the educational system for students. We'll focus on strategies for educational assessment, like work-based learning in contemporary education. Validated questionnaires were used for data collection. This study found that students legitimately participated in survey studies and that learning was difficult.

Keywords: contemporary, education, policy analysis, paradigm shift, assessment tools, modern schooling

Introduction

India is a huge country in terms of both population and land size. There are around two government universities in each Indian city, and each university has 40 departments on its campus. Both traditional and professional courses are offered at these government universities. Transparent, high-quality education and equitable opportunity for all, free from caste-based evaluation, are guaranteed by sustainable development. The agenda/mission for developed India in 2047 is adopted throughout the nation via sustainable development. The present goal of the university is to impart quality education; it ensures that students acquire meaningful knowledge and nurtures them to contribute significantly to the development of the nation. The university system's current objective is to evaluate students' good and negative results. The goal is to highlight how we can offer a learning environment and excellence in education, not to expand the number of schools or departments in the institutions. Nevertheless, following a case study of sixty pupils, some problems never go away: what kinds of evaluation instruments have to be employed to encourage chances for skill development? For instance, even though no one can map the neuronal activity of students' brains, behavioral science allows teachers to assess their students' learning styles and research and methodologies are crucial in determining the character of each student. We look at two dispersed groups from the perspective of the teacher: students with supervised neural activity type and those with unsupervised neural activity type.

Research Problem and Focus

In India, the roots of e-activities have been planted by the Information Communication Technology (ICT) in universities during the spread of the Covid-19 virus, which aimed to integrate information technology into teaching activities. For instance, information technology (IT) was integrated into the part of curriculum at schools, and it was part of teaching activities, playing an essential role/tool in both teaching and learning. An alternative to blackboard and

chalk, it implemented white boards and markers, planted smart classrooms equipped with smart LEDs and projectors. Finally, the focus of IT was not limited to teaching and learning activities, which also aimed to foster mobile technology and the development of various software platforms for communication that was a paradigm shift in technology for teachers and students. However, there are questions after the pandemic wave about whether e-activities are still in teachers' and students' preference [1]. According to the new education policy 2020, it is clearly mentioned that 20-30% of the syllabus should be covered by e-activities. In new education policy students' are free to select one subject of their own choice other than their stream i.e. a science student can choose one subject from art stream. This can cultivate relevant talent and promote values such as enhancing the learning environment. Since 2020, the university is involved in this kind of study. This initiative integrates humanity innovation practices to address issues [2]. These courses emphasize creative thinking to real-world problem. This study involved 60 university students enrolled in the optional subject. Accordingly, the aim of this study was to explore e-learning and option subject of other stream can enhance students' global understanding of sustainability issues. Recently university took an initiative stopped the correspondence course in arts stream and took a new step design online videos lectures and e-content for students.

Research Methodology

There are always some problems with distant learning when a teacher gives lectures to students online, particularly for those students who live in rural areas. Students were anxious about being online, and some of them were unable to connect in class. These kids also have inadequate internet connectivity at home, especially in urban areas. Due to this bad internet connection, some of them have vocal problems. There was also a noticeable drop in attendance; some students joined late for the lecture, and others left midway through. Some of the students are so impoverished that they are unable to buy laptops or cell phones. Because they can engage with the teacher in person, students feel more at ease when learning offline. A major obstacle to reaching their objectives is the absence of practical experience in online form. Students learn and practice questions and answers in offline mode sessions; they can readily expand their understanding and receive feedback and clarification. In online mode occasionally struggle to get electricity because their cell phones are dead so they do not prefer to attend lectures. After e-learning, students also have trouble completing their tasks.

Work-based learning

Some universities have developed skill-based entrepreneurship courses on their own initiative for their students. Universities often build Ministry of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSME) units. Through work-based learning on campus, these MSME units give students practical experience and allow them to start and grow their own businesses. The attitude and conduct of the teacher are also critical to the success of work-based learning. Students are assigned tasks that include objectives created specifically for them in order to improve their understanding of certain concepts, abilities, or values. Teachers who use work-based learning demonstrate creativity, which is a component of thinking skills. Students with thinking skills are able to analyze information, remember facts, and apply knowledge in a variety of contexts. This can have a logical structure and entail a problem-solving mindset in work-based learning. Opportunities for internships with local businesses and industries will be made available to

students enrolled in professional courses. National education policy lays stress on the employability of students' in business and industries. Prominent Indian universities ought to establish campuses abroad in nations that have a high volume of publications and patents. The independent research track record of distinguished individuals should be chosen from among universities that have granted 20 patents and 50 Ph.D. dissertations to establish campuses abroad.

Innovation in Education

NEP envisions technology and innovation working together. Is innovation possible without technology? The foundation for creative and long-term societal growth is education. Where does one think of innovation? Innovation may come from any stream, so it really doesn't matter what field you are in as long as you look about you and consider the areas where you are suffering and where you are missing in your work. We are free to follow our own legitimate educational interests thanks to NEP. However, our NEP is lacking one essential component: universal physical education.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

The following table embodies the details about the enrollment of students in five different activities namely computer science, singing, foreign language, dancing, skill based training:

Activity wise Enrollment of students

Activity	Percentage of students enrolled (out of 60)	Percentage of girls enrolled (out of 20)
Computer science	25%	60 %
singing	12%	20%
Foreign language	20%	25%
dancing	40%	22%
Skill based training	60%	50%

The number of girls enrolled in computer science was 12 out of 20, the number of boys enrolled in computer science 3. Ratio of boys to girls in computer science is equal to 1:4.

Conclusions

The Study Webs of Active Learning for Young Aspiring Minds were introduced by the Government of India's Ministry of Human Resource Development under Digital India, and all advanced education web courses are free to enroll in. Free videos on a variety of courses are also offered by the National Program on Technology Enhanced Learning, which is a significant step for students studying online at home. These videos were very helpful to the students.

Declaration

Author does not have conflict of interest and no funding was available.

References

1. Alqahtani, A.Y, Rajkhan, A.A, E-learning critical success factors during the pandemic COVID-19 Education sciences 10(9), 216 (2020).
2. Chan,M Trend of education research in pre and post COVID-19 Problems of education in the 21st century 80(2),238 (2022).